
**D5.10 Fifth annual report on
dissemination activities to
international stakeholders**

**WP5 Science to Policy
Translation to stakeholders**

Responsible Partner: BfR, SSI

Contributing partners: PMT members

Contents

1.	Summary	4
2.	Highlights	4
3.	Description of activities	5
4.	Evaluation, impact and potential	19

1. Summary

This report describes the dissemination activities of WP5 – Science to Policy Translation of One Health EJP during Y5 (2022). Dissemination activities of WP5 facilitate the uptake of One Health EJP’s outcomes and deliverables by the stakeholders at the national, European, and international level. In addition, given that the consortium will end in 2023, WP5 dissemination activities support the sustainability of One Health EJP-developed results, and play a role in advocating the implementation of the One Health approach at the policy level.

Two Stakeholders Committee Meetings were held, and dissemination activities followed the established strategy (D5.5). WP5 activities targeted national, EU, and international stakeholders, and additional effort was put to create links also with other interested parties not included in the Stakeholders Committee (e.g. private sector, NGOs). WP5 highlighted not only the impact of the One Health EJP in science and policy at European level, but also the impact that One Health EJP-developed solutions can have at the environmental, economic, industrial, and societal level.

The fact that certain One Health EJP-developed solutions are already in use at the national, EU and international level, and the acknowledgment of the One Health EJP activities at stakeholders’ events and in publications, demonstrate the effectiveness of the One Health EJP work in general, and of WP5 dissemination strategy in particular.

2. Highlights

Top achievements:

- Two Scientific Committee Meetings (SCM) were held during Y5 with participation of representatives of Key EU Stakeholders (ECDC, EFSA), EU Agencies (EEA, EMA), international organisations (FAO, WOA, WHO-Euro) and the EU-funded project JPIAMR.
- WP5 continued the organisation of a series of Dissemination Workshops, events targeted at national decision makers and strategic planners, that showcase the impact and benefit that One Health EJP outputs have in the field.
- The One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI), which provides up-to-date information on outcomes scientific projects, was regularly updated, and used to compile important One Health EJP strategic documents (e.g. WP7 led D7.1 and Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda SRIA).

- WP5 was involved in a number of stakeholders' activities, such as consultations, conferences, collaborative papers, and provided other kinds of ad hoc support.
- One Health EJP WP5 was represented in the roles of invited panellist at two key events of EU Agencies: ONE2022 and EFSA's RARA2022
- One Health WP5 was responsible for organizing a high-level round table as a side event at ONE2022 event of EFSA and its sister agencies.
- One Health EJP WP5 was contributor at events organised by others, such as the Geneva Health Forum, International Federation for Tropical Medicine, and AnimalHealth Europe's One Health event.

3. Description of the activities

Dissemination is defined as follows: "The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium." (EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms). Dissemination activities aim at making results and outputs available as widely as possible so that others can use them. Dissemination is thus disclosure of the results in an attractive and user-friendly way. Targeted dissemination focuses on specific audiences that can make best use of the results.

WP5 dissemination activities are complementary to the general dissemination activities of the One Health EJP (by Communications Team and by the Joint Research Projects / Joint Integrated Projects). Scientific publications and other One Health EJP outcomes are quickly made available on the website of the One Health EJP and on the European OpenAIRE program Zenodo. Stakeholders are encouraged to use these materials, and usage is promoted during formal contacts. For example, the Targeted Reports, distributed twice a year to stakeholders' organisations in the form of clickable pdf files, do not only report scientific progress and recent publications of the One Health EJP, but also facilitate linkage with the One Health EJP website, social media, and with projects' webpages and resources.

During Y5, WP5 dissemination efforts focused on strategic dissemination of applicable project outputs and outcomes to national, EU and international stakeholders, and on advocacy activity for the implementation of the One Health approach.

Stakeholders Committee

The **Stakeholders Committee** is a well-established committee consisting of: Key EU Stakeholders ECDC and EFSA, other EU Agencies EEA and EMA, international agencies FAO, WOAAH and WHO Regional Office for Europe (WHO-Euro), and the EU funded project JPIAMR.

The Stakeholders Committee meets regularly twice per year at the **Stakeholders Committee meetings** (SCMs), which are often organised in conjunction with other major One Health EJP events in order to ease the participation of the stakeholders in these events.

The 9th SCM took place on the 13th of April 2022, on the final day of the third Annual Scientific Meeting of One Health EJP (OHEJPASM 2022), and the 10th SCM on the 22nd of November 2022, in conjunction with the joint POC-PMC meeting. The hybrid format of the SCMs made it easier for several delegates from the stakeholders' organisations to participate. The SCMs were appreciated by stakeholders not only to obtain updates on One Health EJP outputs and outcomes, but also to put forward their input into the consortium activities, and to discuss its sustainability.

The 9th SCM was organised at the Fondazione per il Centro Studi, in Orvieto, Italy. It was attended by representatives of Key EU-stakeholders ECDC and EFSA, EEA, FAO, WOAAH (at the time still as OIE), as well as EU-funded project JPIAMR.

The objectives of the meeting were 1) to give an update on current and future activities of the One Health EJP and discuss the involvement of the stakeholders; 2) to discuss the involvement of the stakeholders in the sustainability of the One Health EJP; 3) to update on selected projects. The objectives were fully reached.

To support the dissemination of results from the One Health EJP, representatives of the JIP MATRIX and CARE, were invited to give a brief overview on their outcomes. In addition, stakeholders' future plans and possibilities for cross-sectoral collaboration were discussed, including events such as the ONE2022 and RARA2022, EU policies like the EU4Health Programme (see section "Ad hoc dissemination and support"), and future increased interaction with agencies representing the environmental pillar of One Health (notably EEA). Important part of the discussion was spent to discuss stakeholders' involvement in the SRIA.

The discussion was supported by material which had been provided to all participants beforehand (including the 5th Targeted Report to Key EU Stakeholders). Stakeholders that were not able to attend the meeting were kept up-to-date with background documents, and with the minutes of the meeting.

The 10th SCM was organised at the Public Health Agency of Sweden in Stockholm. It was attended by representatives of the stakeholders' organisations ECDC, EFSA, EEA, EMA, FAO, WOA, and JPIAMR. In addition, representative of REA and additional representatives of stakeholders' organisations were welcomed as observers.

Given that the 10th SCM was the second last SCM, it focused on the future of the One Health EJP and of the European One Health in general. An important document analysing the outcomes and uptake of One Health EJP outputs by stakeholders was discussed (D7.1 Analysis of Outcomes, compiled in collaboration with WP5). Feedback on the SRIA was collected, and participants discussed on the role of stakeholders in upcoming meetings and events of the One Health EJP, as well as the role of the One Health EJP in upcoming stakeholders' initiatives.

The discussion was supported by background documents that the participants received in preparation to the meeting: the 8th Targeted Report to Key EU Stakeholders, the D7.1, and a draft of the SRIA. Stakeholders that were not able to attend the meeting were kept up-to-date with background documents, and with the minutes of the meeting.

Reports

Targeted Reports to Key EU Stakeholders are regular reports disseminated ahead of the SCM meetings (i.e. twice per year). In Y5, two Targeted Reports to Key EU Stakeholders (the 7th and the 8th) were produced. Targeted Reports are a key tool used to disseminate concise and targeted updates, with the objective of keeping the One Health EJP stakeholders up-to-date with 1) the overall One Health EJP consortium; 2) outputs of projects, with focus on those communicated by ECDC and EFSA as being of particular interest; 3) impact achieved by finished projects; 4) recent scientific publications. Although Targeted Reports are aimed at ECDC and EFSA, all the stakeholders' organisations have access to them, and WP5 encourages internal dissemination in the stakeholders' organisations.

While Targeted Reports are for the internal use of stakeholders' agencies, **Reports on Dissemination Workshops** (see section "Dissemination mechanisms: The Dissemination Workshop series") are publicly available. They are uploaded on Zenodo, and are easily findable in the [WP5 webpage](#).

Dissemination mechanisms: The Dissemination Workshop series

During Y5, dedicated WP5-mechanisms of dissemination were addressed at national stakeholders. One of the main tools to reach out to national policy makers, decision makers, and risk managers, were the **Dissemination Workshop series**. Initiated by WP5 during Y4, these workshops focus on the impact of One Health EJP-produced solutions, e.g. case studies on how the solutions have been used in a country, how they were/could be applied in specific situations, and how they benefit the prevention, detection, and response in a One Health fashion. Each Dissemination Workshop is centred around one topic, with several projects contributing to different aspects. The target audience is mainly national stakeholders with decisional power: experts on the level of ministries (e.g. risk managers) and decision/policy makers, however the workshops are also open to EU and international stakeholders (EFSA, ECDC, EEA, EMA, FAO, WOA, WHO-Euro). The final aim of the Dissemination Workshops is to encourage participants to follow the example of colleagues of a different country who have already taken up One Health EJP solutions. Given the varied technical background of the audience, Dissemination Workshops focus on examples of applications rather than on the scientific side, avoiding technical details and using an appropriate language.

Invitations to Dissemination Workshops are disseminated mainly through POC, PMC, SSB and the Stakeholders Committee, with encouragement to forward the invitation to other relevant decision makers in their networks.

Before each workshop, a briefing flyer is produced, with information on the scope of the workshop, and after the workshop a concise report of outcomes (highlights, key messages, recommendations and future needs) is distributed to the participants.

Dissemination Workshops consist of an initial part of presentations by invited scientists, and an important second part of dialogue between the scientists (speakers) and the policy makers (audience). During this phase, needs of both the groups are exchanged, and the discussion highlights how the scientists can support policy makers, and vice versa. This is a unique opportunity for bridging the gaps between science and policy.

The topics of the Dissemination Workshops are based on the interests of the stakeholders, collected with a survey in Y4 and through continuous communications in Y5.

In Y5, two Dissemination Workshops were held. The first dealt with Improving One Health Preparedness to (re)emerging infectious threats. It saw the participation of 110 participants from 17 European countries. The second workshop was organised jointly with the WP4-led Simulation Exercise (SimEx) Team, and focused on the One Health SimEx, which aimed to assess interdisciplinary collaboration capacity and information flow between institutions involved in One Health, public health, animal health and food safety in countries across Europe (the SimEx outcomes were previously presented at ECDC level). It saw the participation of 77 participants from 18 European countries. This Dissemination Workshop was of particular interest as it was based on the collective experience of 11 countries, which reported on One Health practices currently in place and the major gaps identified. These testimonials highlighted the use of the One Health EJP solutions in the field, how the knowledge and innovation stemming from the One Health EJP experience helps in a real-world scenario, and what was the added value of being part of the One Health EJP when responding to a health threat. It highlighted not just benefits, but also shortcomings of the implemented One Health approaches, representing an essential source of information to set up future One Health initiatives.

Interestingly, while in Y4 most of the audience was from food safety sector, in the workshops of Y5 the participants were equally distributed between public health, animal health, and food safety sectors. This improvement could be attributed to a more general interest in the topic, but also to specific dissemination efforts.

After each of the two workshops, an evaluation survey was distributed to the participants. Both the Dissemination Workshops of Y5, similarly to the one in Y4, were evaluated very positively by the participants (e.g. on a score from 1 to 5 to the question “how useful for you personally was it to attend this event?” the average score was 4.1 for both the workshops).

To maximise the impact of the Dissemination Workshops reports, the final reports are uploaded on Zenodo, and made available through the [WP5 webpage](#).

Dissemination mechanisms: national stakeholders' meetings

WP5 presented its achievements in meetings of national stakeholders: the **Programme Owners Committee (POC, i.e. representatives of the relevant Ministries) - Programme Managers Committee (PMC, i.e. Directors General of the beneficiaries) joint meeting** and the **Scientific Steering Board meetings**. The meetings had a particular focus on the impact of the One Health EJP and its projects at the national level.

In particular, at the joint POC-PMC meeting, WP5 chaired a session on the institutionalisation of One Health. The session included contributions of experts from Italy and Sweden, who presented the situation of institutionalisation of One Health at country-level, followed by a discussion with representatives of national and EU stakeholders.

Dissemination at One Health EJP and external meetings and events

Beside the dissemination at internal One Health EJP meetings of national (SSB, PMC, POC-PMC) and EU and international (SCM) stakeholders, WP5 also disseminated its achievements and the achievements of the One Health EJP, by contributions (oral presentations and posters, as well as participation in discussions) at the following events:

- One Health EJP ASM 2022
- 4th International Conference on Animal Surveillance and Health (ICAHS)
- Geneva Health Forum 2022 (see section “Dissemination mechanisms: interaction with other interested parties not included in the Stakeholders Committee”)
- AnimalHealth Europe One Health event (see section “Dissemination mechanisms: interaction with other interested parties not included in the Stakeholders Committee”)
- ONE2022, organised by EFSA and sister EU Agencies
- 9th International Conference on Social Sciences (ICOSS 2022, see section “Dissemination mechanisms: interaction with other interested parties not included in the Stakeholders Committee”)
- Dissemination Workshop series (see section “Dissemination mechanisms: The Dissemination Workshop series”)
- International Congress on Tropical Medicine and Malaria 2020, organised by International Federation of Tropical Medicine

- One Health EJP Final School

Moreover, important additional exchanges with stakeholders' organisation is described in the section "Ad hoc dissemination and support".

Additional dissemination was achieved by WP5 co-authoring peer-reviewed papers:

- Rajendran et al., EPI-Net One Health reporting guideline for antimicrobial consumption and resistance surveillance data: a Delphi approach (2022). *The Lancet Regional Health – Europe*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanepe.2022.100563>
- Bronzwaer et al., One Health collaboration with and among EU Agencies – Bridging research and policy (2022). *One Health*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2022.100464>
- Benedetti et al., Search term "One Health" remains of limited use to identify relevant scientific publications: Denmark as a case study. (2022). *Frontiers in Public Health*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.938460>
- Streichert et al., Participation in One Health Networks and Involvement in the COVID-19 Pandemic Response: A Global Study. (2022). *Frontiers in Public Health*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.830893>

Dissemination activities of WP5 are not unilateral. The information not only flows from the One Health EJP to the stakeholders' organisations, and is then distributed within the organisations, but the One Health EJP's vast network is also made available to the stakeholders. This **dissemination from stakeholders to the One Health EJP** is kindly requested by the stakeholders, which recognise the value of the One Health EJP network of cross-sectoral experts. One example was the dissemination of the call for One Health AMR Network, requested by EMA, the WHO/Euro call for experts to join the WHO/Euro's Advisory Group on One Health, and the GOARN requests for assistance (which are dedicated to GOARN partners).

Ad hoc dissemination and support

In order to support policy initiatives and to advocate the One Health approach at the EU and international level, WP5, with the support of the Coordination Team, contributes to relevant **stakeholders' consultations and strategic discussions and events**. Relevant opportunities are identified thanks to the activity "scanning of stakeholders' documents", informal communications,

but also through direct request of the stakeholders. During Y5, WP5 gave input on behalf of the One Health EJP to the following stakeholders' consultations, discussions and events:

- ToR of the Partner Platform of the Tripartite's One Health Regional Coordination Mechanism (which the One Health EJP joined in Y4), and subsequent discussion on how to best support the One Health Regional Coordination Mechanism through targeted dissemination of One Health EJP-developed solutions.
- JPIAMR SRIA and Prevention and Interventions Roundtables
- PREZODE co-construction workshops and discussions
- Participation in EFSA Advisory forum
- EU4Health programme 2023: The One Health EJP participated in the open consultation, and was subsequently invited to the stakeholders' event where it presented its experience and proposition for the future of One Health within EU4Health
- Consultation of the EU Global Health Strategy
- Invited as panellist at EFSA's ONE2022 session "Making a difference: bridging EU research and policy", next to representatives from the European Parliament, EEA, EFSA, EMA and ECHA, moderated by a representative of ECDC.
- The One Health EJP organised a dedicated side event at ONE2022
- Invited as panellist at EFSA's RARA 2022, in the opening session round table discussion.

In almost all of the aforementioned cases, the contribution and support of One Health EJP was requested directly by the stakeholders. This indicates the success of the One Health EJP: that through years of thoughtful interaction with the stakeholders, trust required to take part in strategic planning of EU and international organisations has been built.

The One Health EJP's contribution to stakeholders' consultations and events was followed by additional interactions, resulting in additional output. For example the panel discussion at EFSA'S ONE2022 that WP5 representative contributed to, resulted in an important strategic paper co-authored

with representatives of EU Agencies ([Bronzwaer et al., 2022](#)), where the benefit of the science-policy interaction of the One Health EJP is acknowledged.

Among the aforementioned events, the ONE2022 should be noticed. ONE2022 was organised by EFSA and its sister agencies ECDC, ECHA, EEA, EMA and JRC. In the frame of the conference, the One Health EJP organised a side event.

WP5, in collaboration with the One Health EJP Communications Team, organised the side event entitled “[One Health European Joint Programme: Lessons learnt from a European multidisciplinary initiative](#)”. The objectives of the event were to introduce the One Health EJP, to inspire and encourage all (from early career colleagues to high-level stakeholders) to learn about the One Health approach, to share experiences of working in a multidisciplinary environment and to reflect on the One Health approach along with the benefits of cross-sectoral collaborations from a personal and professional development point of view at institutional, national and European level. The side event took the form of a high-level round table discussion, and saw participation of representatives of ECDC, EFSA, One Health High Level Expert Panel, WHO-Euro, the MedVetNet Association, as well as representatives of the One Health EJP PMT and projects. The hybrid nature of the event allowed broad participation.

Some activities of WP5 deal with the issues of long-term sustainability and future needs of stakeholders. To reach maximum impact of results and to avoid duplication of efforts, WP5 collaborated with WP7 in the drafting of the Strategic Integrative Research Agenda (SRIA, in preparation), as well as deliverable D7.1 “Analysis of outcomes and uptake of EJP’s outputs by stakeholders”, in particular part III “Analysis of outcomes of the OHEJP likely to be utilised by stakeholders also beyond the EJP”. This consists of a list of outcomes describing protocols, databases and other tools and solutions expected to contribute to the work of four prominent stakeholders: ECDC, EFSA, DG-AGRI and DG-SANTE, but that could be of interest also for other stakeholders. A summarised version of such list was created by the Communications Team and is available on the [WP5 webpage](#).

Dissemination mechanisms: interaction with other interested parties not included in the Stakeholders Committee

As the One Health approach evolves becoming more inclusive and integrating more disciplines, it was deemed relevant of the One Health EJP to search connections with interested parties not included in the Stakeholders Committee, for example those coming from the social sciences, or private sector.

During the previous reporting year (Y4), a collaboration was set up with the One Health Commission and with WHO-GOARN. A global survey was ran together with the two organisations to examine the value of One Health workforce and of One Health networks in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. This resulted in a joint publication in Y5 ([Streichert et al., 2022](#)). Based on this collaboration, an additional collaboration was initiated with the One Health Social Sciences Initiative (a sub-group of the One Health Commission). An oral presentation was accepted for the 9th International Conference on Social Sciences, and further work is ongoing.

Another example of interactions with sectors other than public health, animal health and food safety, is the participation, after invitation, to the Geneva Health Forum 2022, an event notably engaged by NGOs, funding bodies, and humanitarian associations. The One Health EJP was not just invited to contribute to the main conference, but also to share its expertise in two workshops: one on One Health education activities, and another on science-policy interface. This initial collaboration evolved further, and resulted in a joint manuscript (in revision).

Possible impact on the private sector was demonstrated by WP5 being invited in the panel discussion “The balancing act of public, animal and environmental health. How to translate this to policy?” of AnimalHealth Europe, an association of veterinary drugs manufactures. The One Health EJP was invited to join the event alongside the WOAAH, DG-SANTE, WHO-Euro and other prominent organisations.

Scanning of stakeholders’ documents

WP5 carries on regular **scanning of stakeholders’ documents** (scanning around 50 webpages of relevant institutions and organisations including ECDC, EFSA, EC relevant DGs, EEA, EMA, FAO, WOAAH, WHO) in order to identify relevant new research and integrative needs of stakeholders and

establish interactions where complementarity may be feasible. Information extracted following this process is summarised in monthly reports and made available to the One Health EJP consortium members and to the stakeholders by uploading the reports in the groups of the One Health EJP website.

When pressing information is identified, it is timely disseminated, before the publication of the monthly report, to the PMT, Project Leaders, or Communications Team, as appropriate, to support their dissemination efforts and networking. This activity has led to a number of activities and actions, for example the One Health EJP's contributions to stakeholders' consultations.

The One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI) and the Data Management Plans (DMP)

The activities of the One Health EJP consortium are numerous and diverse. WP5 makes sure that the results from One Health EJP are made readily available for policy and decision making through targeted dissemination to the stakeholders. For example, WP5 curates the **One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI)**.

The OHOI highlights outcomes of the One Health EJP, supports dissemination of results of the various activities (e.g. research projects, integrative activities), and depicts to some extent complementarity with activities outside the One Health EJP. The OHOI is a public online database accessible to all. As such, it targets also stakeholders and other interested parties not represented in the Stakeholders Committee, and supports internal and external collaboration and dissemination. The OHOI has been identified as a valuable tool for dissemination of results of the One Health EJP to national and international stakeholders, to other One Health initiatives, as well as within the One Health EJP, for example to minimize the risk of duplication of. Beside this, in Y5 it was also used as the starting point for compiling the table of D7.1 "Analysis of outcomes of the OHEJP likely to be utilised by stakeholders also beyond the EJP" (see section "Ad hoc dissemination and support").

Briefly, the OHOI is an online database inventorying and cataloguing the outcomes of scientific projects and overarching activities of the One Health EJP. It is accessible from the [One Health EJP website](#).

The OHOI lists and organises the outcome of the consortium (databases, biobanks, computational methods, pieces of hardware, etc.), gives general information on the specific outcomes, highlights the

added value by depicting to a certain extent similar activities in place outside of the consortium, and links to specific resources that are available. Most importantly, it gives the contact information of the persons in charge, facilitating contacts in case more insights are desired. The OHOI has a search function to ease navigation and to browse the inventory.

Y5 saw a major change in the user interface of the OHOI, which is the migration of the Updates section into the Archive section. The Updates section was a section of the OHOI listing timely updates of each project. Feedback gathered during Y5 pointed out the overwhelming amount of information in the Updates section (more than 1000 entries), and discussion centred around how to make the information more focused, while maintaining optimal transparency. It was decided to move all the entries of the Updates section in the Archive, while keeping in the foreground the outcomes, which were seen as most useful.

The Archive section of the OHOI – which is also public – now stores old updates of the projects in the form of a downloadable Excel file.

In addition to these technical upgrades, in terms of content two major updates of the OHOI were performed during Y5, as well as ad hoc updates as new information became available and needed to be disseminated. To date, the OHOI lists 160 outcomes (without considering the entries in the Archive section, which are more than 1000).

It was further decided to keep the OHOI available after the end of the One Health EJP as a repository of outcomes developed within the consortium. After September 2023, the OHOI will still be available through the One Health EJP website and through the MedVetNet Association website.

The OHOI is advertised on newsletters, at meetings, at international conferences, on the One Health EJP website, and through other means (for example it was published in the introduction of MATRIX/ORION OHS Codex/KIP).

To avoid duplication of efforts within the One Health EJP and to support dissemination, WP5 is also involved in the **Data Management Plan (DMP)** committee, led by WP4.

The DMP committee supports JRPs and JIPs to draft and publish their respective DMPs. WP5 was involved in the evaluation of final DMPs of finished projects, and took care that they were correctly

uploaded on Zenodo and available through the [dedicated webpage](#), focusing on the FAIRness of the data. One example of such increased FAIRness is the fact that some DMP data are available already before the end of a project (normally DMPs become available only after the end of the project), thus improving the transparency of the One Health EJP consortium and timeliness of dissemination.

Given the similarity of scopes between the DMP and the OHOI, to maximise their added value and avoid duplication of work, the DMP webpage is reachable also through the OHOI.

The DMP work sparked a case study on the search term “One Health”, published as a paper with contribution of a WP5 representative ([Benedetti et al. 2022](#)).

The Stakeholder Conference

The main forum for dissemination to and interaction with a broad range of stakeholders will be the **Y6 Stakeholder Conference**. This three-day event will take place on 19-21 June 2023, at the end of the One Health EJP in order to have all the deliverables and outcomes available, to allow maximum exploitation of results.

The Stakeholder Conference will be the occasion to have additional impact at the policy and scientific level, but also at the societal and economic level.

Given this ambitious aim, the target audience will be a broad group of different stakeholders and other interested parties, including: departments and executive agencies of the European Commission, Agencies of the EU, associations dealing with human, animal, and environmental health, being they from the private sector, citizen, farmers, or patients associations, NGOs, general and specialised press.

During Y5, WP5 set up a Stakeholder Conference Working Group, which drafted a first version of the conference agenda. It was decided to have presentations from One Health EJP projects focusing on impact and potential impact of developed solution, in order to encourage the stakeholders to pick them up. In addition, high-level speakers and panellists will be invited from EC DGs, EU Agencies, international agencies, consumer associations, NGOs etc.

It was decided to hold the conference in Brussels, to ease the participation of many speakers whose organisations are based there. After extended research, a suitable venue was found, the Comics Art Museum, and exchanges are ongoing to secure it.

It was also decided to hold the conference as a hybrid event, to maximise impact. Technical solutions in this direction have been discussed with a specialised company, and, at the time of writing, work is ongoing to secure technical support.

Additional work is ongoing to address other practical aspects like catering, accommodation etc.

With the support of the Communications Team, a website [was launched](#), and work is ongoing to prepare the launch of registration in early 2023.

Content and organisation of the Stakeholder Conference has been regularly discussed within the One Health EJP, and also with the stakeholders, for example at the 10th Stakeholders Committee meeting (see section Stakeholders Committee)

Main dissemination plans for Year 6

In Y6, the main task related with dissemination of WP5 will be the organisation of the Stakeholders Conference, as well as its promotion taking advantage of all available channels, and creating new ones.

WP5 dissemination activities will continue actively in Y6, and they will build on the established connections and success of the activities in Y1-Y5. As scientific projects (except the JIP COVRIN) will end in Y5, the availability of finalised outcomes will represent the chance to disseminate ready-to-use solutions to the stakeholders and to other interested parties, expanding the means described in the dissemination strategy (D5.5). Other major dissemination activities, beside from the aforementioned Stakeholder Conference, will be the final Dissemination Workshops, and the 11th and last SCM. Focus of the dissemination activities during the landing phase of the One Health EJP will be on the benefit that One Health EJP-developed solutions can bring when applied, and on the impact that they are already having at the national, EU and international level.

Ad hoc dissemination opportunities will be taken advantage of to disseminate the impact of the One Health EJP, and to advocate One Health approach.

During Y6, the OHOI will be updated once more by WP5 in collaboration with the Project Leaders, and following users' requests as they come up. Solutions found to ensure its sustainability will be deployed.

One final Targeted Reports to Key EU Stakeholders will be written and distributed to the stakeholders before the last SCM.

WP5 will keep collaborating with the other overarching WPs of the One Health EJP, in particular with the Communications Team, with WP4 supporting the DMP committee, and with WP7 supporting overall sustainability of the One Health EJP. Information on policy and research needs of stakeholders will be gathered by WP5 through contacts with EU and international organisations represented in the Stakeholders Committee, and through regular scanning of stakeholders' documents.

4. Evaluation, impact and potential

WP5 - Science to Policy Translation was active and successful in its dissemination activities during Y5. The structures for efficient dissemination are in place, in use, and were further adjusted and refined based on dialogue with the stakeholders. Maintaining dialogue with Key EU Stakeholders, national stakeholders (e.g. through Dissemination Workshops), identifying and disseminating the impact of One Health EJP, and supporting global actions, were all successfully achieved. In addition, recognising the need for a more inclusive One Health approach, interactions were initiated with a number of interested parties not included in the Stakeholders Committee, and particular focus will be given to them in the Y6 Stakeholder Conference.

Overall, the science-policy interface of the One Health EJP, curated by WP5, received positive feedback from the stakeholders not just in meetings internal of the One Health EJP, like SCM meetings and meetings of national stakeholders (e.g. POC-PMC), but also publicly at events of EU Agencies (e.g. RARA, ONE2022), and in written form (e.g. [Bronzwaer et al., 2022](#)).

One Health EJP was invited to contribute to important events of EU Agencies, in particular ONE2022, where it also hosted a dedicated side event with the contribution of prestigious speakers, and EFSA's RARA2022. These invitations vouch for the trust created between EU Agencies and the One Health EJP, and the high regard that stakeholders hold the One Health EJP in. Moreover, the One Health EJP attracted other interested parties, resulting in invitation to contribute to events such as the Geneva Health Forum and AnimalHealth Europe's One Health event.

The success of dissemination efforts of WP5 and of the One Health EJP as a whole are demonstrated by the solutions of its scientific projects being applied at the national, EU and international level, and by One Health EJP overarching results and lessons learnt being used to shape strategic plans at the policy level.

The success of the advocacy activities of WP5, promoting the implementation of the One Health approach, may have contributed to the observation that One Health approach is now specified in several strategic documents of stakeholders. For example, the One Health approach is found among the work areas of WHO-GOARN 2022-2026 strategy (One Health EJP advocated for the inclusion of One Health during the Global Meeting of Partners in December 2021), and in the EU4Health work programme 2023 (the One Health EJP presented its consultation at EC level).

Recognising the benefit of the work of the One Health EJP, stakeholders also played a role in the broader dissemination of One Health EJP calls and tools through their newsletters (e.g. EFSA and One Health Commission newsletters), websites (e.g. One Health Tools & Toolkits page of the One Health Commission), and toolkits (TZG SISOT).

The fact that stakeholders trust the One Health EJP to distribute calls in its network (e.g. EMA, WHO/Euro, see section Dissemination at One Health EJP and external meetings and events above) vouches for the trust created between stakeholders and the One Health EJP.